

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Tox controls lifespan and immunity related to aging.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We used here cells engineered to lack Tox4 to demonstrate and describe a likely function for the Tox family of nuclear receptors in control of lifespan and immunity related to aging.

1 Results

- 2
- 3 a. Tox4 KO K562 cells
- 4 b. Selective interferon gene product control by Tox4
- 5 i. Ifitm2 and Ifitm3 control
- 6 c. Tox4 controls expression of an Fc receptor, FCGR2A.
- 7 d. Metabolic control by Tox4.
- 8 i. Galactose mutarose *GALM*
- 9 ii. Phosphoglycerate dehydrogenase *PHGDH*
- 10 e. Tox4 influences T-cell activation.
- 11 i. Control of Lcp2
- 12 ii. Tox4 deletion results in loss of Lyz expression.
- 13 f. Tox4 loss activates the nuclear prelamin A recognition factor, NARF.
- 14 g. Mucin regulation by Tox4.
- 15
- 16
- 17
- 18
- 19
- 20
- 21
- 22
- 23
- 24
- 25
- 26
- 27
- 28

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Citations

1. Wang, L., Yu, J., Zhou, Q., Wang, X., Mukhanova, M., Du, W., Sun, L., Pajvani, U.B. and Accili, D., 2022. TOX4, an insulin receptor-independent regulator of hepatic glucose production, is activated in diabetic liver. *Cell metabolism*, 34(1), pp.158-170.